

Kinetic Studies on the Reaction of Cellulose with Iodoacetic Acid and Thermogravimetric Analysis of the Products

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Reaction of cellulose with monoiodoacetic acid has been studied kinetically. The degree of substitution has been obtained by determining the percentage of iodine. The rate constants and various thermodynamic parameters for the esterification reaction have been calculated by assuming it to be a second order reaction. The kinetics of pyrolysis of iodoacetylated cellulose has been studied by isothermal thermogravimetry. The mass loss versus time curves at different temperatures for the treated samples have been plotted and the values of the rate constant k' obtained from the slopes of these curves. The energies of activation for the degradation and the corresponding entropies and free energies of activation have been calculated by using two different methods. Results obtained by both the methods are in good agreement. It has been found that with increase in the degree of substitution the energy of activation and entropy of activation register a decrease while the free energy of activation remains constant.

CELLULOSE as a polyhydroxy alcohol offers the possibility of ester formation with many organic acids. A large number of cellulose derivatives have been synthesized¹⁻³ which include esters of inorganic and organic acids, ethers and graft copolymers, but relatively few have achieved commercial importance.

Kinetics of the reaction and thermal degradation of cellulose and cellulose derivatives were studied by various investigators⁴⁻⁶. Schwenker⁷⁻¹⁰, Patel¹¹ and Bhatnagar¹² have carried out studies on the thermal degradation and characterization of cellulose and cellulose derivatives by differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Chatterjee and Schwenker¹³ made use of DTA to determine the degree of substitution of cellulose derivatives. They indicated that in the DTA curves, parameters of peak height and peak area correlate linearly with the degree of substitution.

In the present investigation, kinetics of the reaction of cellulose with iodoacetic acid, and the thermal degradation of the resultant products by isothermal thermogravimetry have been studied. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for the chemical reactions and thermal degradation have been calculated.

Experimental

Reagents :

- (i) Cellulose, supplied by M/s Dassel, West Germany, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride under vacuum.
- (ii) Chlorobenzene, supplied by M/s Sarabhai M. Chemicals, India, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and the distillate at 132° collected for use.

- (iii) Iodoacetic acid, rectified (B.D.H.), dried under vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride.
- (iv) Perchloric acid (60%), supplied by M/s Riedel-De Haenag, Seelze-Hannover, Germany.
- (v) Potassium hydroxide, Sarabhai M. Chemicals, India.
- (vi) Alcohol, absolute alcohol was used.
- (vii) Silver nitrate and nitric acid were AR grade reagents.

Method of acetylation : Cellulose iodoacetate with different degrees of substitution was prepared in chlorobenzene using monoiodoacetic acid (3 moles for each mole of anhydroglucose units of cellulose) under various reaction conditions. Each time, 1.62 g cellulose was allowed to get swollen in 10 ml chlorobenzene for 1 hr at the temperature of the experiment. This was done to increase the reactivity of cellulose. Iodoacetic acid (5.58 g) was dissolved in chlorobenzene (20 ml) and allowed to attain the temperature of the experiment. 0.5 ml of perchloric acid was added and the solution transferred to a three necked flask containing the cellulose. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred for the desired period while passing a current of nitrogen at the temperature of the experiment. The product was first washed with chlorobenzene and then with benzene. It was then dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 at room temperature. The iodoacetylated samples, which were found to be highly hygroscopic, were stored in vacuum desiccator containing P_2O_5 , KOH and $CaCl_2$.

The reaction products were identified by elemental analysis and ir spectra.

Elemental analysis: The % of iodine in the samples was estimated by Seeker and Mathewson method¹⁴.

Infrared spectral analysis: Infrared spectra of the samples in KBr pellets were obtained using Beckman model IR-20 spectrophotometer. Each sample (0.5-1.0 mg) was intimately mixed with 100 mg of dry powdered potassium bromide and its infrared spectrum recorded.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The TGA studies were carried out isothermally at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mm using a quartz spring balance. The detailed procedure for carrying out the TGA studies has been described elsewhere¹².

The apparatus described earlier¹² was modified slightly for these studies. The stopcock used for taking the sample in the delivery tube was replaced by a V-shaped sample tube having a B-14 cone at one end and closed at the other end. The angle between the two limbs of the sample tube was 120°. This could be fitted in the B-14 socket joined to the delivery tube at an angle of 120°. The sample was taken in the closed end of the sample tube which was then fitted into the delivery tube with the closed end pointing downwards. After the temperature had become constant and the vacuum was 10⁻⁴ mm, the sample tube was rotated about the joint so that the closed end pointed upwards and the sample went down the delivery tube into the platinum crucible.

Results and Discussion

(a) The infrared spectra of the treated samples exhibited strong absorption at 1745 cm⁻¹ due to stretching vibration of C=O bond in the ester group formed as a result of the reaction. A relative decrease in the intensity of hydroxyl band at 3600 cm⁻¹ was also observed. The presence of the band at 1100 cm⁻¹ in the sample was due to the pyranose ring structure. The infrared spectral studies indicated that the ester formation of cellulose with iodoacetic acid had taken place.

From the percentage (X) of iodine in the sample, the degree of substitution (p) of the various samples were calculated using the equation¹⁵,

$$p = \frac{162X}{12700 - 168X} \quad \dots (1)$$

where 162 is the molecular weight of anhydroglucose unit, 127 is the atomic weight of iodine and 168 represents the net increase in the molecular weight of the treated cellulose resulting from the introduction of one substituent, i.e., -OOCCH₂I, in any one of the anhydroglucose units. The values of the degree of substitution of the various samples are given in Table 1.

(b) If 'a' represents the initial concentration of -OH groups of cellulose, 'b' the concentration of the -OH groups at any time 't' and 'p' the number of the -OH groups per anhydroglucose unit that

TABLE 1—DEGREE OF SUBSTITUTION OF THE TREATED SAMPLES AS A FUNCTION OF TIME

Time in hr	% I (X)	Degree of substitution (p)	p/(3-p)
Temp. 30°			
1	1.27	0.017	0.0055
2	2.00	0.026	0.0098
3	3.51	0.047	0.0158
4	4.51	0.061	0.0208
5	5.45	0.075	0.0256
6	6.33	0.088	0.0300
Temp. 40°			
1	1.39	0.022	0.0073
2	2.73	0.036	0.0122
3	4.05	0.055	0.0185
4	5.50	0.076	0.0259
5	6.62	0.093	0.0318
6	7.74	0.102	0.0352
Temp. 50°			
1	1.33	0.024	0.0080
1.5	2.68	0.036	0.0120
2	3.55	0.048	0.0161
3	5.09	0.069	0.0240
4	6.32	0.088	0.0302
5	7.03	0.099	0.0341
Temp. 60°			
1	2.51	0.033	0.0111
1.5	2.87	0.038	0.0128
2	3.57	0.048	0.0166
3	5.77	0.080	0.0273
4	7.34	0.104	0.0360
5	7.81	0.111	0.0385
Temp. 70°			
1	2.86	0.038	0.0128
1.5	4.35	0.059	0.0200
2	5.400	0.074	0.0253
3	8.140	0.116	0.0403
4	9.84	0.136	0.0474
5	9.55	0.139	0.0487

Values of k_r as calculated by least square method at different temperatures are: 30°—6.984 × 10⁻⁷; 40°—8.235 × 10⁻⁷; 50°—9.274 × 10⁻⁷; 60°—10.910 × 10⁻⁷ and 70°—13.208 × 10⁻⁷ l mol⁻¹s⁻¹.

have reacted (degree of substitution) with -COOH groups during time t, then

$$b = (1 - p/3)a \quad \dots (2)$$

where p/3 is the fraction of the hydroxyl groups per anhydroglucose unit that have reacted in time t.

Assuming that the reactivity of the primary and the secondary hydroxyl groups of cellulose is the same and independent of the chain length, the rate equation can be represented by

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [-OH] = k_r [-COOH] [-OH] \quad \dots (3)$$

If the initial concentration of the -OH groups of cellulose is the same as that of the -COOH groups of iodoacetic acid then the rate constant (k_r) is given by

$$k_r = \frac{p}{a(3-p)t} \quad \dots (4)$$

Thus the average values of the specific reaction rate, k , for the various systems have been calculated from the plots of $p/(3-p)$ versus time, which were found to be linear (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on the reaction of cellulose with iodoacetic acid.

The experimental energy of activation, ΔE_{exp} , and the frequency factor, A , have been calculated using the Arrhenius equation by plotting a graph of $\ln k$, against T^{-1} which was found to be linear in the temperature range of the reaction. The values of ΔE_{exp} and A obtained by the method of least squares were found to be $13.41 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $7.1 \times 10^8 \text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{sec}^{-1}$, respectively.

At 323K, the average temperature of the experiment, the entropy of activation, ΔS^* , was calculated using the equation $e^{\Delta S^*/R} = Ah/e^{kT}$, where R is the gas constant, k is the Boltzmann constant, T is average temperature of the reaction in K, and h is the Planck's constant. The value of entropy of activation was found to be -180 J deg^{-1} .

The values of ΔH^* and ΔG^* were found to be $10.72 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $68.92 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively at 323K.

Thermogravimetric analysis : Iodoacetylated samples of cellulose with different degrees of substitution obtained by treating cellulose with monoiodoacetic acid at 30 and 40° for 2 hr were subjected to TGA studies.

The thermal degradation of the two samples at different temperatures was studied by observing the decrease in weight with time. The plots of weight versus time of the sample treated with iodoacetic acid at 30° are shown in Fig. 2. The shape of the curves for the rate of weight loss of sample treated at 40° is of the same nature.

It is observed that initially there is a small but rapid mass loss followed by a major mass loss. The rate of the major mass loss remains constant for the maximum portion of the curve, then decreases and ultimately the mass becomes constant.

Fig. 2. Plots of weight versus time for the thermal degradation of cellulose treated with iodoacetic acid at 30° for 2 hr.

○ 561.16K, □ 545.96K, △ 535.56K, ▽ 515.16K

Evaluation of kinetic parameters : The degree of degradation (α) was calculated using the equation $\alpha = (w_i - w_t)/(w_i - w_r)$, where w_i , w_t and w_r represent the initial weight, weight at time 't' and the final weight of the sample, respectively. The rate constant k' for the thermal degradation of treated samples was determined with the help of the equation

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{0.5} = (u/r)t \quad \dots (5)$$

which describes a reaction rate controlled by the movement of an interface at constant velocity (u), for a disc or cylinder¹⁶ of radius r . The rate constant k' given by u/r is obtained from the slopes of the plots of $1 - (1 - \alpha)^{0.5}$ versus time which are linear passing through the origin as shown in Fig. 3. The values of the rate constant k' were also calculated by the method of least squares. The plots of $\ln k'$ versus T^{-1} for the two samples are shown in Fig. 4.

The values of the energy of activation, ΔE^* , the frequency factor, A , the entropy of activation, ΔS^* , and the free energy of activation, ΔG^* , for the cellulose treated with monoiodoacetic acid at 30 and 40° for 2 hr are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Plots for the thermal degradation of cellulose treated with iodoacetic acid at 30° for 2 hr.

Fig. 4. $\ln k'$ versus $1/T$ plots for the thermal degradation of cellulose treated with iodoacetic acid for 2 hr at (a) 30° and (b) 40°.

The energies of activation have also been calculated by Jacobs and Kureishy's method according to which at a given temperature T_1 ,

$$F(\alpha_{n+1}) - F(\alpha_n) = k_1(t_{n+1} - t_n) \quad \dots (6)$$

where α_{n+1} and α_n are the degrees of degradation at times t_{n+1} and t_n , respectively, and $F(\alpha)$ is a function of the degree of degradation. If the same experiment is repeated at a different temperature T_2 , then for the same values of α Eq. (6) becomes

$$F(\alpha_{n+1}) - F(\alpha_n) = k'_1(t'_{n+1} - t'_n) \quad \dots (7)$$

By combining Eqs. (6) and (7) with the Arrhenius equation it can be shown that

$$\frac{t_{n+1} - t_n}{t'_{n+1} - t'_n} = \frac{e^{-\Delta E^*/RT_2}}{e^{-\Delta E^*/RT_1}} \quad \dots (8)$$

The plots of $\ln(t_{n+1} - t_n)$ against T^{-1} are linear with slope $\Delta E^*/R$ and are shown in Fig. 5. The values of energy of activation obtained by this method are also listed in Table 2 which are in good agreement with those obtained from Eq. 5.

It was observed that the values of the energy of activation for the pyrolytic degradation of the

Fig 5. Jacob and Kureishy's plots for thermal degradation of cellulose treated with monoiodoacetic acid at (a) 30° and (b) 40° for 2 hr.

TABLE 2—DEGREE OF SUBSTITUTION, ENERGY OF ACTIVATION, FREE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION AND TEMPERATURE RANGE OF THE THERMAL DEGRADATION OF VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	Degree of substitution (p)	ΔE^*	ΔE^*	A (S ⁻¹)	Average temp of the expt. (K)	ΔS^* and ΔG^* at average temp of the experiment		Temp range of the expt. (K)
		(kJ mol ⁻¹) (using Eq. 5)	(kJ mol ⁻¹) (using Eq. 6)			ΔS^* (J deg ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
1. Cellulose treated with monoiodoacetic acid at 30° for 2 hr	0.0262	82.56	81.78	7.46×10^4	539.46	-156.82	170.40	515.16-561.16
2. Cellulose treated with monoiodoacetic acid at 40° for 2 hr	0.0361	66.07	66.02	1.49×10^5	571.46	-187.61	171.17	555.56-586.56

iodoacetylated cellulose were less than that of pure cellulose. The values of the energy of activation have been found to decrease with the increase in the degree of substitution. The value decreased from 82.6 to 66 kJ mol⁻¹ as the degree of substitution increased from 0.026 to 0.036. This means that the charring temperature of the treated samples is lower than that of pure cellulose and decreases with increasing degree of substitution, indicating that the treated samples are better flame resistant.

The entropy of activation for the thermal degradation was negative in all the cases and decreased with increase in the degree of substitution. This is due to the fact that decrease in the degrees of freedom accompanying the formation of the activated complex goes on increasing with the increase in the degree of substitution.

The free energy of activation for the process was almost constant, suggesting that the basic mechanism of thermal degradation in all the iodoacetylated samples is the same. It is suggested that hydrogen iodide is given out as the first volatile product in this case and all the other volatile substances given out on pyrolysis of cellulose¹⁷ are produced later at different stages of degradation.

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